

OPTIMIZATION OF IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITES USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS AND EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS

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1 Abstract

Optimization is becoming common practice in all the engineering applications of late. While, there are a lot of literature and research available on the optimization of certain designs but at times there are problems in engineering where the exact nature of variables that affect the cost function are not known. In such cases, it is very difficult to get a good optimized solution since it depends upon the understanding of the researcher which parameters to base the cost function upon. A procedure for the design optimization of the composite laminated structures under the low velocity impact loads has been presented in this study.

The optimization process is performed using Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm. The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) was used to train the model which forms the cost function. The optimization problem of impact loads on composite laminates depends upon a multitude of variables and to identify the most influential variables, a sensitivity analysis approach was performed prior to the optimization process. The product of the cost and the amount of energy absorbed was selected as the single cost function while the parameters used for optimization included the number of layers, thickness of layers and the stacking sequence as well as the type of fiber used.

The approach adopted here has been proved to be very versatile and can be applied for a number of optimization problems where the unavailability of the cost function and its dependence is not known.

2 Introduction

The optimization of the impact resistance of the composite plates and pipes against low velocity impact loads is important in terms of a number of advantages. Optimized solutions are lighter in weight hence saving materials and resulting in low cost efficient products. Generally, optimization is performed on a selected function commonly termed as the cost function which is the function of several variables.

This study outlines a procedure for the optimization of carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy based composite plates from the initial sensitivity analysis approach to the final optimization algorithm. A four level approach has been used for this purpose. A flow chart describing the steps from the model validation to the optimization is shown in Fig. 1.

Sensitivity analysis is a tool employed in engineering problems to identify the influence of input parameters on the state variables such as displacements, stresses, strains and temperature etc.

The result of sensitivity analysis is the identification of a limited set of state or input variables that have greater influence on the output of the system. The main aim of the sensitivity analysis is the calculation of the sensitivity coefficients [1] which is obtained by the variation of input variables one at a time or in groups and study the variation in the output variable [2]. The methodology of using sensitivity analysis is a common practice in for almost all types of numerical techniques [3]; Boundary Element Method (BEM) [4], Finite Difference Method (FDM) [4], Finite Element Method (FEM) [5] as well as hybrid and meshless strategies [6,7]. This approach has been successfully applied in a wide variety of applications and is used here to identify the most crucial factors for impact resistance.

ANN models proved to be excellent tool in the approximation and interpolation in a variety of applications. ANN has been used in function fitting and prediction of various mechanical properties and damage mechanisms in composite materials. ANN models are very efficient for modeling and predicting the non-linear behavior of different systems. El Kadi [8] has presented a comprehensive review of the neural networks and the different approaches within them. The applications of ANN are in the manufacturing process optimization as well as in the monitoring and modeling the manufacturing and the mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced composites. Bezerra et al. [9] used ANN to predict the shear stress-strain behavior of carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy fabric composites. ANN models give the ability to predict the amount of energy absorbed for a particular set of inputs. This ability can be employed in the optimization problem. Since, we can use ANN models to generate a large set of data for use with optimization algorithms like genetic and differential algorithms.

Fig. 1. Flow Chart of the proposed methodology

There is a rich literature available where different optimization algorithms have been implemented in similar problems. Almeida et al. [10] used genetic algorithms for the design optimization of the composite laminated structures. The authors have discussed the adaptation of the terminologies and developing codes to use them with GA. Lee et al [11] have used evolutionary algorithms for the multilayered composite structure design optimization. The objective of their study was the optimization of the stacking sequence of the composite plates.

2.1 FE Model and Validation

For the purpose of this study, the data required to train ANN models was collected through numerical simulations using commercial FEA software ABAQUS explicit. As it is a common practice in numerical studies, the numerical model had to be validated against already verified numerical or experimental results. Therefore, a numerical model was chosen from the study of Yokoyama et al [12], the study by Yokoyama et al. was based upon experimental and numerical results. The experimental results were based upon the thesis of Biase EHC., and also presented in the study of Yokoyama et al, and the same model was developed in the ABAQUS to verify the model.

The geometric dimensions of the composite plate and the impactor and also the stacking sequence of the plate are provided in Table 1. The material considered in the analysis is a woven fabric of either Carbon/Epoxy system or Glass/Epoxy system, for validation however carbon/epoxy composite plates were used. The geometry of the composite plate is 2-D which is meshed using the S4R shell elements; the load is applied in the form of initial velocity to the impactor which equates to 27.55 J of energy at the time of impact. The boundary conditions are considered to be rigid fixed at the two shorter ends, since the model is simplified using quarter symmetry; symmetric boundary conditions have been applied as well on the appropriate edges of symmetry.

Table 1: Geometric Dimensions of the composite plate and impactor

Composite Plate		Impactor	
Length	102 mm	Diameter	12.7 mm
Width	152 mm	Mass	1.5 kg
Thickness	4.2 mm	Velocity	6.0608 m/s

The results reported in the study by Yokoyama et al. [12] are used to validate the results. Our study reveals a much closer result to the experimental values.

In the Table 2, the results are shown for the experimental and numerical results from the previous studies for both the Hashin model and the model proposed by Yokoyama et al. and compared with our results using the Hashin model. Fig. 2 gives the time history plot of displacement of the center node of the plate and compares the results from all the reported results from Yokoyama at al. [12] with the results from this study.

Fig. 2. Maximum displacement for the composite plate with respect to time. Experimental and numerical results for displacement-time curve from Yokoyama et al. [12]

Table 2: Results from Yokoyama et al. and the comparison with our results

	Experimental (Yokoyama) [12]	Numerical (Yokoyama-Proposed Model) [12]	Numerical (Yokoyama-Hashin Model) [12]	Current Result	Error (%age)
Max. Disp. (m)	0.006018	0.00611	0.00592	0.006062	0.7 %
Time of Impact Event (s)	0.0036	0.00354	0.00328	0.00338	6.1 %

2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

In the first phase of the study, a sensitivity analysis was performed and a select few variables with high influence on the impact performance has been obtained. The main aim of the sensitivity analysis is the calculation of the sensitivity coefficients [1] which is obtained by the variation of input variables one at a time or in groups and study the variation in the output variable [2]. The variables shortlisted were related with either the material characteristics or the geometric characteristics of the composite plates.

In a previous study by the authors [13], a sensitivity analysis was performed in order to investigate the effects of various material and geometric properties on the impact performance of the

composite plates. The factors considered to have an effect on the impact performances are listed in Table 3 along with the normalized sensitivity coefficients (NSC) calculated for each case.

The output variable for sensitivity analysis is chosen to be the dissipated impact energy or the energy absorbed during the impact event. The validated model was selected as the nominal case and the amount of absorbed energy for the nominal case was found to be 4.74 J.

The normalized sensitivity coefficient is given by

$$NSC_{X_i} = \left(\frac{\partial Y}{\bar{Y}} \frac{\bar{X}_i}{\partial X_i} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where, ∂Y is the change in output variable Y from the nominal value \bar{Y} , where ∂X_i is the change in input variable from the nominal value given by \bar{X}_i .

This study demonstrated the important factors upon which the impact resistance of a composite plate depends. The values of the NSC for these factors are plotted in Fig. 3, where it can be observed that the values of NSC for factors such as thickness, tensile strength etc. is considerably higher than others. Based on these results, a study using design of experiments is carried out with the factors considered are:

- 1) Thickness of each layer/ply
 - 2) Stacking Sequence
 - 3) Tensile strength in the fiber direction
 - 4) Number of layers
 - 5) Fracture toughness in the fiber direction
- during tensile loading

Table 3: Sorted list of the parameters according to normalized sensitivity coefficient (NSC)

No.	Symbol	Energy absorbed in X+ΔX (J)	Energy absorbed in X-ΔX (J)	NSC
X1	Tp	4.59	5.16	1.4096
X3	St	5.59	5.34	0.2899
X10	Xt	4.66	4.87	0.2001
X2	N	4.77	4.88	0.0609
X15	Gf ^t	4.70	4.81	0.0479
X5	E22 = E33	4.80	4.70	0.0440
X4	E11	4.77	4.72	0.0117
X6	v12 = v13	4.78	4.75	0.0056
X16	Gf ^c	4.74	4.77	0.0042
X8	G12 = G13	4.74	4.76	0.0024
X11	Xc	4.77	4.75	0.0015
X17	Gm ^t	4.76	4.74	0.0014
X13	Yc	4.77	4.75	8.22 X 10 ⁻⁴
X14	S12	4.74	4.75	3.89 X 10 ⁻⁴
X12	Yt	4.75	4.76	3.35 X 10 ⁻⁴
X18	Gm ^c	4.76	4.76	1.69 X 10 ⁻⁴
X7	v23	4.76	4.76	1.28 X 10 ⁻⁴
X9	G23	4.74	4.73	6.4 X 10 ⁻⁶

Fig. 3. NSC for all the variables demonstrating the relative effect of each on the absorbed impact energy

2.3 Design of Experiments

A study was then performed based on the Design of Experiments approach which generates a matrix for the variables selected by Sensitivity Analysis approach. Design of experiments is a very efficient statistical technique which can be employed in various experimental investigations [14]. The design of experiments provides the capability to understand the design effects of various factors and their statistical significance as well [15]. The variables used for the study were the layer thickness, orientation of layers and number of layers. The size of the DOE matrix is important for further study where a Neural Network model is trained for the purpose of prediction of absorbed impact energy. A total of 108 experiments each were performed numerically on the carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy composite plates. The factors that are considered in the DOE study and the different levels of each factor studied are listed in the Table 4 and Table 5 for the CFRP and GFRP plates respectively.

Table 4: DOE Table for CFRP plates

Thickness		Number of Layers		Stacking Sequence	
Factor	Levels	Factor	Levels	Factor	Levels
0.12	1	16	1	[0/30/60/90]	1
0.14	2	20	2	[45/-45/0/90]	2
0.16	3	24	3	[45/30/-30/-45]	3
0.18	4	28	4	[60/45/-45/-60]	4
0.2	5	32	5		
0.25	6	36	6		
0.3	7				
0.35	8				
0.4	9				

Table 5: DOE Table for GFRP Plates

Thickness (mm)		Number of Layers		Stacking Sequence	
Factor	Levels	Factor	Levels	Factor	Levels
0.25	1	24	1	[0/30/60/90]	1
0.3	2	28	2	[45/-45/0/90]	2
0.35	3	32	3	[45/30/-30/-45]	3
0.4	4	36	4	[60/45/-45/-60]	4
0.45	5				
0.5	6				
0.6	7				

The material properties of the Carbon/Epoxy and the Glass/Epoxy system are listed in Table 6. The results were calculated in terms of the absorbed energy with the impact energy fixed at 27.55 J. The impactor dimensions, weight and velocity are being kept constant in all the cases. The boundary conditions are also kept the same throughout all the experiments. The simulations were performed in ABAQUS Explicit environment.

Table 6: Material Properties of the composite materials used in the study

	Carbon/Epoxy	Glass/Epoxy
Elastic Properties		
E ₁ (GPa)	60.8	26
E ₂ (GPa)	58.25	26
E ₃ (GPa)	-	8
G ₁₂ (GPa)	4.55	3.8
G ₁₃ (GPa)	4.55	2.8
G ₂₃ (GPa)	5	2.8
ν ₁₂	0.07	0.1
ν ₁₃	0.07	0.25
ν ₂₃	0.4	0.25
Ply Strengths		
X _t (MPa)	621	414
X _c (MPa)	760	458
Y _t (MPa)	594	414
Y _c (MPa)	707	458
S ₁₂ (MPa)	125	105
S ₂₃ (MPa)	125	65

Intralaminar Fracture Toughness

G_f^t (KJ/m ²)	160	10
G_f^c (KJ/m ²)	25	1.562
G_m^t (KJ/m ²)	10	0.625
G_m^c (KJ/m ²)	2.25	0.14
G_s (KJ/m ²)	2.25	0.14

2.4 Artificial Neural Network

ANN models are a very powerful method since they can be applied to any generic problem with few inputs and can be trained to learn from them with the expected outputs. ANN models proved to be excellent tool in the approximation and interpolation in a variety of applications [9,16–19]. It is an adaptive system whose structure is modifiable based on the external or internal information that flows through the network. The ability of ANN model to learn by example highly non-linear and noisy data is useful in our approach where we are dealing with statistical data. This feature is very useful in our problem where a mathematical relationship of the factors considered by sensitivity analysis with the absorbed impact energy is not available but with the help of FEA simulations a lot of training data is available to us.

A neuron is a real function of the input vector (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k). The training function for the neurons, available with MATLAB are tan-sigmoid, pure linear and log-sigmoid. For the training of input neurons, tangent sigmoid (tansig) is used which is given as

$$f(x) = \frac{2}{(1 + e^{-2x}) - 1} \tag{2}$$

This function is equivalent to tangent-hyperbolic function $\tanh(x)$ available in MATLAB but is usually faster. For the neurons providing connections to the output layer, a pure linear transfer function is used.

$$f(x) = x \tag{3}$$

A detailed discussion about the neural network modeling has been discussed in the authors’ previous

work [20]. A simple version of single layer of hidden neurons used in this study is represented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. General Configuration of Artificial Neural Network for composite plates

This prediction model is very important for the purpose of optimization. As only a small number of cases were simulated for the composite plates, therefore the accuracy of this model is very crucial for the validity of the proposed optimized solution.

An Artificial Neural Network was trained using the data set provided by the DOE run. To find the best configuration for ANN model i.e., the number of neurons and hidden layers, a number of different configurations were tried and the root mean square error was compared. A final model with RMSE of 0.08 J and maximum error of 0.62 J was selected. This model consisted of 21 neurons and the correlation with the target data is plotted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Correlation between the predicted and the target response for CFRP plates

A similar ANN model was trained to predict the glass/epoxy composite plates. The ANN model for glass fiber plates uses 24 neurons in a single layer and is able to predict the amount of absorbed energy with maximum error of 1.1047 J and root mean square error of 0.33 J as represented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Correlation between the predicted and the target response for GFRP plates

An independent data set was used to test the ANN models' accuracies for both the CFRP and GFRP plates and the results were found to be within acceptable range. The test and the results are listed in Table 7 and Table 8

Table 7: Independent test cases to verify ANN model for CFRP plates

Inputs (thickness, layers, stacking sequence)	Actual response (Abaqus) J	Simulated Response (ANN) J	Difference
0.24,24,1	5.9006	5.9836	-0.083
0.16,30,4	4.6322	5.0069	-0.3747
0.22,26,2	4.6903	4.9347	-0.2444
0.14,18,3	7.7589	8.5684	-0.8095
0.36,32,2	0.5093	0.6132	-0.1039

Table 8: Independent test cases to verify ANN model for GFRP plates

Inputs (thickness, layers, stacking sequence)	Actual response (Abaqus) J	Simulated Response (ANN) J	Difference
0.26,24,2	13.37359	15.5417	2.1681
0.42,30,4	6.14928	6.2809	0.1316
0.35,26,1	12.69973	13.153	0.4532
0.54,34,2	0.602984	0.6865	0.0835
0.36,36,3	8.449098	8.3282	-0.1209

2.5 Cost Models

Composite materials and their production is an expensive process. It has always been the focus of major design and development teams to reduce the costs while simultaneously achieve maximum performance. The idea for this study is optimizing the impact performance with respect to the costs. To estimate the costs related to the composite plates and pipes, it is necessary to develop a cost model which can relate the costs of the material and the production with the samples. A simple yet realistic cost model is proposed in this section, the cost model we adopted here is given by:

$$CF = X + [(C1/100) + (C2/100)] * X \quad (4)$$

In this equation, CF represents the total costs, whereas we assume X to be the material costs. In general, material costs are considered to be the maximum and the other costs like labor costs 'C1' and the other overheads 'C2' are considered to be some fraction of the material costs.

An online survey for the prices of the different types of fibers gave a basic idea of the material costs. The prices listed in the **Error! Reference source not found.** are for a reference and may vary depending upon a number of factors ranging from the supplier to the texture of the fiber.

Table 9: Material costs of different types of fibers

Material	Type	Price
Carbon fiber	Woven fabric	200 USD per m ²
Glass fiber	Woven fabric	12 USD per m ²
Carbon fiber	Unidirectional	900 USD per kg
Glass fiber	Unidirectional	30 USD per kg

Based on these prices for the materials used in the manufacturing of composite plates and pipes, it is obvious that the optimization with respect to the cost is important.

2.6 Differential Evolution Algorithm

Differential evolution algorithms were developed in mid 90s as an optimization technique by Rainer Storn and Kenneth Price. It is a simple and robust population based optimization technique with few control variables and fast convergence. Being an evolutionary algorithm, the DE technique is suited for solving non-linear and non-differentiable optimization problems. DE is a kind of search technique which works on finding the candidate solution among a population. DE algorithms generate new populations from the existing one based on certain parameters like mutations and crossovers.

For the purpose of optimization based on the variables selected earlier, a Differential Evolution algorithm was selected. The selection of DE algorithm is based upon the fact that the variation of absorbed energy by the composite plate with respect to the variables is not a linear function and DE is considered to be very adaptable for non-linear and non-differentiable optimization problems and is used effectively by Lee et al [11]. An appropriate population size and number of generations is required for the convergence of the optimized results.

For our problem, we use an initial population size of 200, with a crossover of 0.8 and a total of 100 generations to find the optimal solution.

2.7 Optimization

For GFRP plates, a series of runs of the optimization algorithm was performed; it was found that the optimal solution is a plate having 36 numbers of layers using stacking sequence 4 with the thickness of each layer to be about 0.57 mm. At this configuration, the ANN model predicts the absorbed energy by the plate to be 0.004 J. and assuming the price listed in Table 9, the cost is estimated to be 14 USD.

Similarly, for CFRP plates, the optimal solution was found to be plate with 32 layers of stacking sequence 1 and the thickness of each layer to 0.38 mm. This configuration will weigh about 0.29 kg and the amount of absorbed energy as predicted by our ANN model is 0.102 J. The cost of this plate would be around 260 USD.

3 Conclusions

The results suggest that this procedure for optimization is reliable and robust. The approach discussed here can be applied to a number of optimization problems for the composite structures. In this study, we tried to present a complete flow of the optimization problems in cases where a mathematical model is difficult to obtain. The approach presented here is applicable to structural optimization of composite materials under a variety of loads. The main conclusions from this study can be summarized as:

- Sensitivity analysis is a useful tool in determining the factors influencing the most on the impact performance of the FRP plates and pipes.
- ANN models are very strong and useful tools for the function fitting of non-linear behavior and as observed in the case of CFRP plates are able to predict the absorbed energy with very little error.
- The accuracy of the ANN models depend upon the behavior of the training data sets, if there are too much sudden variations in the training data as was

observed in the results from the composite pipes then the model can be prone to errors.

- Using the optimization algorithm, it was suggested that the optimal stacking sequence for the flat plates would be the sequence number 4 from this study.

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